

Students' Academic Achievement at University as Determined by their Communication Skills

Ashfaqe Ahmed Shah*

Syeda Zunaira Fatima[†]Uzma Shahzadi[‡]

Vol. V, No. I (Spring 2020)

Pages: 10 – 18

DOI: [10.31703/gesr.2020\(V-II\).02](https://doi.org/10.31703/gesr.2020(V-II).02)

Abstract: *This study investigates into the academic achievement (AA) of university students as determined by their Communication Skills (CS). The effect was measured on the basis of gender, locality, semester and program of study. The researchers developed their research instrument by adapting from two questionnaires. One was the research instrument used at the College of Physiotherapists of Ontario (n.d.); and the other was the "Questionnaire-Verbal Communication" (Pierre Desrosiers, n.d.). Taking Sargodha district as the population, conveniently sampled 160 students from the University of Sargodha were surveyed through the questionnaire. The study was quantitative in nature. The findings of the study concluded that n students' CS yielded any effect on their AA. Also, the students at all levels (semesters) and in all programs were reported to have equivalent level of CS. However, it was interesting to note that the level of both CS was prominently higher as perceived by the students.*

Key Words: Higher education, learning, outcomes

Introduction

Communication Skills (CS) include the ability to use language proficiently. These are the expertise that student have to practice themselves before they enter in working world ([Iksan, et.al, 2011](#)). Communication is an act of transferring data starting with one place then to the next. Everyone wants to communicate effectively considering the purpose to share ideas and information. According to "Aristotle" man is a social animal; so, we cannot live without society. To live in a society, we must have to communicate with others. For better and effective communication, we need some skills. CS are the skills which everyone must have. In our daily life activities, we need to communicate with others for different purposes. Students need such skills in completion of their degree because if they have such skills, they may present the ideas in an effective manner. Developing CS among students may benefit them in all aspects of their life as personal life, social gathering, professional life etc. Expression is very important in every one's life; and effective CS are the basic element of best expression. Good communication is considered very important at all level. Communication is a main tool to form relationships on the way to make more grounded relations among two individuals or a group of individuals. Without communication human relations are hard to be maintained. To be effective, a man needs an incorporated arrangement of CS. These abilities comprise composing ability, discourse abilities, listening aptitudes, and nonverbal aptitudes (Malootra, n.d). During job interviews, the CS of new graduates do matter a lot. So, universities and staff need to make sure if the learners are trained in the skill to talk efficiently. The students should develop their CS in a broad as well as inclusive way. Students actually have to extend their expertise to do well within their chosen occupation ([Ihmeideh, et al. 2010](#)).

Communication Skills (CS) include the ability to use language proficiently. These are the abilities that student must prepare themselves earlier than they go into the world of work ([Iksan, et.al, 2011](#)). Such abilities are important in helping students to perform well academically ([Iksan, et.al, 2011](#)). AA is the result of learning the degree to which a learner has accomplished their learning objectives. The learners' AA assumes an essential element producing excellent quality graduates capable to be awesome pioneer

* Assistant Professor, Department of Education, University of Sargodha, Punjab, Pakistan.

[†] Lecturer, Department of Education, University of Sargodha, Punjab, Pakistan.

[‡] Assistant Professor, Department of Education, University of Sargodha, Punjab, Pakistan.

Email: uzma.shahzadi@uos.edu.pk

([Mushtaq & Khan, 2012](#)). AA prepares students for their future success in both education as well as the world of work. AA is the performance of a student and usually measured in the term of GPA/CGPA (Malootra, n.d).

Several studies have been reported in the field of CS, but present research investigated into the university students' AA under the effect of their CS. The result from this study provided valuable information about CS to students in many ways. This study might be supportive to improve the students' CS. This study may be helpful to improve students' CGPA. This would be beneficial to all the stakeholders including teachers, parents, policy makers etc.

Review of Literature

Inner Social Course (ISC) and Outer Social Course (OSC) are the two main factors influencing the student's AA ([Mushtaq & Khan, 2012](#)). The former factors contain student's English language competence, class-plans, class-size, the textbooks, test-results, learning-facilities, home-assignments, class-environment, course-material problems, in-class instructor's role, innovations used in the class, and exams-plan. The later factors contain for example parents' occupation, and plethora of social, professional and financial issues.

Research literature demonstrated that students' AA is the outcome of various factors, for example, personnel, sex, age etc etc. [Abdullah AL Mutairi \(2011\)](#) maintained that the students' AA heavily depends upon their previous learning and especially their level of CS in English Language and this had conclusively been evidenced in the literature. As cited by [Iksan, et.al, 2011](#) in general, communication is explained as exchanging information from the individual throughout verbal and non- verbal ways. All the changes in society are hinged upon ([Mahmud 2013](#)) the studies in communications and verbal ability of the individuals. As referred to by Serkan (2014) the spirit, who is a social being, for quite a long time is in dealings with the world. To express his feeling, perspective, thoughts and Bob hope through talking and composing and expected them to be comprehended by presentation and tuning in; he attempted to delight his need. The accurate use of communication additionally encourages good quality relationship. Not just can dialect and discourse test influence one's learning capacities, it moreover influences the public capacities, for example, making friends, increasing healthy connections, as well as accomplishing a boosted self-assurance. This self-assurance might help student in putting additional attempt for executing fine. Like a student of university who has been prepared toward begins for selected profession, he or else she ought to accept the open door in every action that enhanced CS in an extra broad as well as whole perspective therefore that such abilities be able to be completely developed.

Learners necessitate placing effort to build up their CS to have the capacity to do well in their chosen line of work ([Ihmeideh, 2010](#)). As cited by [Mushtaq & Khan, 2012](#) school, college and universities enclose no value with a student. Students are the most important resources for an institute of higher education. Societal as well as financial advancement of a state relies on the university student's AA. The student's AAs assumes an essential element in conveying the most excellent class former students who will obtain to elect extraordinary pioneer as well as struggle intended for the country during this mode in charge of the state economic as well as public development ([Ali, 2009](#)). Learner's AA opinion has received impressive thought in the earlier period researches; it is difficult aspect of educational literature, as well as science student performance is inclined as of public, psychological, monetary, and ecological and person basics. These elements firmly have an effect on the performance of student; however, these variables change from individual to individual along with state toward state.

AA is usually observed the same as on the whole brilliance of student in their studies. As indicated by [Brockman & Russell \(2012\)](#), learners of the 21st century which had an objective of making educational progress have to focus on understanding, composing, as well as math as well as to figure out how to adjust public abilities collectively among aspects of educational inherently provoked, objective leaning otherwise somewhat depicted while publicly communicatively capable in every perspectives. These elements know how to be in frequent types and one of them is the determined method for determining rating or else scores. University students' AA is evidenced directly through their CGPAs (Cumulative

Grade Point Averages). For this situation, learners who have been self-motivated in their learning which mean they do fine all through, will bit by bit score high CGPAs.

Methodology

This section addressed methodology of research and procedures utilized in this study. According to [Leedy & Ormrod \(2001\)](#), research methodology is “the common approach the researcher use for execution the research project”. Present research was to study effect of the CS on the students’ AA (CGPAs) at university level. Following procedures were adapted for this study. This part described the strategies of data collection, the research procedure and the technique of sampling that was utilized to choose the respondents of the study. In order to make this study a systematic one the researcher designed clearly defined procedure right from conception to conclusion. Quantitative research technique was used to analyse the data.

It was a descriptive research. Survey strategy was used. In this design the researcher administers a survey through an adapted questionnaire to a small group of people (sample) to recognize the tendency in attitude, views, behaviours, or else attributes of a large gathering of people (Creswell, 2012 a). The population of the study includes all the student of BS, BEd, MA, and MPhil program in main and the sub campuses of the university. Accessible population was the main campus students. The researcher personally collected data from 160 male and female students of BS, BEd, MA, and MPhil from the University of Sargodha. Researcher carefully self-administered the questionnaires to conveniently accessible sample (as suggested by [Gay & Mills, 2011](#)) to collect the data. The researchers developed their research instrument by adapting the questionnaires from two different studies. One was used at the College of Physiotherapists of Ontario (n.d.); and the other instrument was the “Questionnaire-Verbal Communication” by Pierrete Desrosiers (n.d.).

This instrument appeared to be more suitable because it was simple to answer. A five point rating scale was used. After the adaption of research instrument there were 23 items in it. Pilot study was conducted to estimate the internal consistency of the questionnaire. Questionnaires were administered to the small number of the conveniently selected sample. To determine reliability, the data thus collected were analyzed on computer by SPSS. The reliability of the data was found to be 0.600.

Table 1.

“Cronbach’s Alpha”	“N of Items”
Pilot Testing	0.600
	23

Data were analyzed through descriptive (frequency, mean, median, mode, variance, Standard Deviation) and inferential techniques (t-test, Analysis of Variance and linear regression) using SPSS. The values of t-test (independent samples) helped understand the difference in gender and locality of the university students; the One-Way ANOVA helped understand the difference among students of different semesters and programs of the university; and the linear regression estimated the effect of the CS (predictors) on the AA (outcome) of university students. Researcher used following equation of linear regression:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \epsilon$$

Y represents AA **α** represents intercept, **β_1** is the coefficient of **X_1** which represents CS, and the values of **β_1** denote the effect size of the corresponding variables (predictor).

Results

This section presented analyses as well as interpretation of the data. Major purpose of the study was to find out the effect of CS of university students on their AA. This section has two parts i.e. analysis through **descriptive** and **inferential** statistics.

In descriptive part of statistics, explanation of the sample is discussed while testing of the hypothesis and understanding of the consequences are specified in inferential part of this chapter. Frequencies and

Percentages of the responses were recorded as under.

Table 2. Gender Distribution

Gender	Frequency (%)
Male	59 (36.9)
Female	90 (56.2)
Not mentioned	11 (06.9)
Total	160 (100)

Table 1 showed that total respondents of the study were comprised 59 male students and 90 female students. Among the respondents 36.9% were males and 56.2% were females. Frequencies and percentages of the responses were presented below.

Table 3. Locality Distribution

Locality	Frequency (%)
Urban	96 (60)
Rural	64 (40)
Total	160 (100)

Table 2 explained that out of 160 university students 96 were from urban areas while 64 were from rural areas. On the whole 60.0% students were from urban locality while 40.0% students were from rural locality. Frequencies and percentages of the responses were described in the following.

Table 4. Sample distribution of sample

Semester	Frequency	Percentage
1	03	01.9
2	76	47.5
4	43	26.9
5	01	00.6
6	24	15.0
8	13	08.1
Total	160	100.0

Table 3 showed that out of 160 university students, 3(1.9%) students were from 1st Semester, 76(47.5%) from 2nd Semester, 43(26.9%) from 4th Semester, 1(0.6%) from 5th semester, 24(15.0%) from 6th Semester and 13(8.1%) from 8th semester of their study program. Frequencies and percentages of the responses were produced in the following table.

Table 5. Sample distribution of the programme

Program	Frequency	Percent
BS	75	46.9
Masters	71	44.4
BEd	4	2.5
MPhil	10	6.2
Total	160	100.0

Table 4 showed that out of 160 university students, 75(46.9%) students were from BS program, 71(44.4%) students were from master's program, 4(2.5%) students were from BEd program and 10(6.2%) students were from MPhil program.

Table 6. Frequency and Percentage Response of Sample

CS	SA	A	UD	DA	SD
1. Paraphrasing of words	18 (11.2)	108 (67.5)	21 (13.1)	8 (5.0)	5 (3.1)
2. Ability to present ideas orally.	41 (25.6)	79 (49.4)	25 (15.6)	14 (8.8)	1 (0.6)
3. Ability to communicate effectively	38 (23.8)	90 (56.2)	23 (14.4)	8 (5.0)	1 (0.6)
4. Writing error free grammatical report.	16 (10.0)	71 (44.4)	39 (24.4)	26 (16.2)	8 (5.0)
5. Ability to verbally comprehend the messages.	24 (15.0)	79 (49.4)	41 (25.6)	13 (8.1)	3 (1.9)
6. Absorbing written material quickly.	27 (16.9)	73 (45.6)	40 (25.0)	18 (11.2)	2 (1.2)
7. Cooperation with peer group.	83 (51.9)	67 (41.9)	7 (4.4)	1 (0.6)	2 (1.2)
8. Paying attention to nonverbal cues...	35 (21.9)	67 (41.9)	32 (20.0)	22 (13.8)	3 (1.9)
9. Acceptance of criticism.	34 (21.2)	77 (48.1)	31 (19.4)	11 (6.9)	7 (4.4)
10. Ability to bear criticism calmly.	28 (17.5)	84 (52.5)	32 (20.0)	13 (8.1)	3 (1.9)
11. Expressing disagreement.	31 (19.4)	68 (42.5)	40 (25.0)	17 (10.6)	4 (2.5)
12. Encouraging others for clarification of their thoughts.	38 (23.8)	91 (56.9)	18 (11.2)	11 (6.9)	2 (1.2)
13. Acceptance of suggestions at workplace.	40 (25.0)	82 (51.2)	22 (13.8)	13 (8.1)	3 (1.9)

Description of Sample

In Table 7, mean, mode, median, standard deviation and variance were represented of the 23 statements of the instrument. The range of all the statements is “4”.

Table 7. Descriptive Statistic of Sample

CS	Mean	Median	Mode	SD	Variance
1. Ability to paraphrase words	2.2	2.2	2.0	0.8	0.7
2. Presentation of oral ideas.	2.1	2.0	2.0	0.9	0.8
3. I have ability to communicate effectively and appropriately.	2.0	2.0	2.0	0.8	0.6
3. Ability to communicate effectively	2.6	2.0	2.0	1.0	1.1
4. Writing error free grammatical report.	2.3	2.0	2.0	0.9	0.8
5. Ability to verbally comprehend the messages.	2.3	2.0	2.0	0.9	0.9
6. Absorbing written material quickly.	1.6	1.0	1.0	0.7	0.5
7. Cooperation with peer group.	2.6	2.0	2.0	3.5	11.9
8. Paying attention to nonverbal cues...	2.3	2.0	2.0	1.0	1.0
9. Acceptance of criticism.	2.2	2.0	2.0	0.9	0.8
10. Ability to bear criticism calmly.	2.3	2.0	2.0	1.0	1.0
11. Expressing disagreement.	2.1	2.0	2.0	0.9	0.7
12. Encouraging others for clarification of their thoughts.	2.1	2.0	2.0	0.9	0.9
13. Acceptance of suggestions at workplace.					

In Table 7 the value of $t=0.803$ and significant difference i.e. 0.313 illustrated that there was insignificant difference; both male and female students had comparable level of CS.

Table 8. Gender Difference

Gender	N	Mean	SD	SE Mean	t	P
Female	90	30.766	7.060	.74419	.313	.803
Male	59	31.135	7.006	.91211		

In Table 8 the value of $t=1.402$ and significant difference i.e. 0.054 demonstrated that there was insignificant difference regarding locality background of the students. The students having urban and rural family background had comparable level of CS.

Table 9. Locality Difference

Locality	N	Mean	SD	SE Mean	t	P
Urban	96	31.447	7.8711	.8033	1.402	0.054
Rural	64	29.906	4.8064	.60081		

In Table 9 the value of $F(27,132) = 1.072$ and significant difference i.e. 0.382 explained that there was insignificant difference among the CS of students from different semesters.

Table 10. Semester wise difference

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Squares	F	P
Within Groups	503.137	132	3.812	1.072	0.382
Between Groups	110.363	27	4.088		
Total	613.500	159			

Similar level of CS had been noted among students of all the semesters.

Table 11. Program wise difference

	Sum Squares	Df	Mean Squares	F	Sig
Within Groups	90.998	132	.689	0.631	0.918
Between Groups	11.745	27	.435		
Total	102.744	158			

In Table 11 the value of $F(27,132) = 0.631$ and significant difference i.e. 0.918 indicated that there was insignificant difference; and therefore, equivalent level of CS was noted for the students of all the programs.

Following was the regression equation to estimate the effect of CS on AA of university students.

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_i + \epsilon$$

Y represents academic Achievement (AA), α represents the intercept, β_1 is the coefficient of X_i , i.e. CS. The value of β_1 represented the effect size of the independent variable (predictor). Details about effect of CS on AA were described below.

Table 12. Summary of the Impact of CS Model

R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	SE
0.091	0.008	0.002	1.031

Table 12 indicated that the value of R^2 indicated that the model was very weak to explain the variance in the dependent variable (i.e. AA) under the effect of the independent variable (i.e. CS). Details about impact of CS on AA are presented as below.

Table 13. Impact of CS

	Unstandardized		Standardized	t	P
	β	SE	β		
Constant	2.985	0.378		7.904	0.000
CS	-0.014	0.012	-0.091	-1.145	0.254

In Table 13 the value of significant difference i.e. 0.254 illustrated that there was insignificant difference and therefore the null hypothesis (There was no statistically significant effect of CS on AA) was failed to be rejected. Students' CS had not made any impact on their AA.

Discussion

CS include the ability to use language efficiently. These are the abilities that student must equip themselves earlier than they enter in professional life (Iksan, et.al, 2012). Such skills are important in helping students to perform well academically. These are the skills required by all the students irrespective of gender and locality of their residence. Present research confirmed the same truth for the students studying at University of Sargodha, Pakistan. Moreover, the students from all the programs at all levels (semesters) were reported to be similar but the level of the acquired skills was prominently greater. A study "CS among university students", found that students of university have accomplished good quality CS (Iksan, et.al, 2012). Unlikely to the findings of the present study, [Tabish & Iqbal \(2015\)](#) found that fluency levels in CS of rural boys and girls are much less than those of the urban sample ([Tabish & Iqbal 2015](#)). Many other studies (for example, [Fazel & Aghamolaei 2011](#)) evidenced statistically insignificant gender difference among students.

Differing with the findings of the current research, a study titled as "Communication Aptitude and Academic Success" indicated that achieving proficiency in verbal communications is essential to students to do good academically (Mahmud, M. M 2014). Through useful communication, learners can study to get the correct abilities, thoughts; ideas as well as plans are able to be created by communicating efficiently. Students' presentation skills are dependent of their CS. A student with better communication skills (CS) will certainly be able to perform better in a range of other related educational performance. The research revealed both of the congruous as well as incongruous results in current research project and at the same time, noted the matching phenomena in the literature.

Conclusion

CS include the ability to use language efficiently. These are the abilities that student must equip themselves earlier than they enter in professional life (Iksan, et.al, 2012). Such skills are important in helping students to perform well academically. These are the skills required by all the students irrespective of gender and locality of their residence. Present research confirmed the same truth for the students studying at University of Sargodha, Pakistan. Moreover, the students from all the programs at all levels (semesters) were reported to be similar but the level of the acquired skills was prominently greater. A study "CS among university students", found that students of university have accomplished good quality CS (Iksan, et.al, 2012).

It was found that fluency levels (CS) of rural boys and girls are much less than those of the urban sample ([Tabish & Iqbal, 2015](#)). On the other hand, there was another study, where statistically insignificant gender difference among students were reported regarding their CS ([Fazel & Aghamolaei, 2011](#)). Differing with the findings of the current research, a study titled as "Communication Aptitude and Academic Success" indicated that achieving proficiency in verbal communications is essential to students to do good academically (Mahmud, M. M. 2014). Through useful communication, learners can study to get the correct abilities, thoughts; ideas as well as plans are able to be created by communicating efficiently. Students' ability in spoken communication can as well enhance their presentation (communication) skills.

Through useful communication, learners can study to get the correct abilities, thoughts; ideas as

Well as plans are able to be created by communicating efficiently. The study intended to investigate the effect of CS on the AA of university students.

The CS were found to be alike among male, female, urban and rural university students. Similarly, the students at all levels (semesters) and in all programmes were reported to be possessed of comparable level of CS. CS was eminent to be higher as perceived by the university students.

Recommendations

A larger and more diversified sample would have yielded different picture of the outcome. It was recommended that future researcher should make use of other variables to observe the relationship between AA and CS. The similar study should be carried out in other universities to get more comprehensive representation. The reliability of research instrument was 0.600; it was recommended for further studies that researcher should carry out item analysis before adaptation of these instruments.

References

- Ali, N., Ali, S., Mokhtar, N., & Salamat, A. S. (2009). The Factors Influencing Students' Performance, *Management Science and Engineering*, 2-3.
- Birch, W.J. B. & Abdel-Salam, G. A.S (2013). Several Nonparametric and Semi parametric Approaches to Linear Mixed Model Regression, *Journal of Statistical Computation and Simulation*.
- Fazel, I., & Aghamolaei, T. (2011). Attitude towards learning CS. *Acta Medica Iranica*, 3-4.
- Gay, L. R., & Mills, G. E. (2011). *Educational Research; competencies for analysis*. New York: Pearson.
- Skills for Learning Questionnaire (College of Physiotherapists of Ontario), was accessible on the following URL: http://www.collegept.org/Assets/Resources%20%20QM/QMF_Skills_LearningQuestionnaire.pdf. Questionnaire-verbal communication (Desrosiers) was accessible on the following URL:http://pierrettedesrosiers.com/documents/QUEST_verbal_communication_JG_001.pdf.
- Ihmeideh, F. M., Al-Omari, A. A., & Al-Dababneh, K. A. (2010). Attitudes toward CS among Students-Teachers in Jordanian Public Universities. *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*, 3.
- Iksan, Z. H., Zakaria, E., Meerah, T. S., Osman, K., Lian, D. K., Mahmud, S. N. (2011). CS among university students, *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 2-3.
- Leedy & Ormrod, 2001, retrieved On June 14, 2016 from https://www.google.com.pk/search?q=Leedy+%26+Ormrod%2C+2001%29%2C+research+methodology&oq=Leedy+%26+Ormrod%2C+2001%29%2C+research+methodology&gs_l=serp.3...749256.753366.0.753836.16.7.0.0.0.0.343.343.3-1.1.0....0...1c.1j2.64.serp..15.0.0.qHkpf8rxP1g.
- Mahmud, M. M. (2013). Communication aptitude and academic success. *Procedia social and behavioral sciences*, 2, 3, 4.
- Mahmud, M. M. (2013). Communication aptitude and academic success. *Procedia – Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 2, 3, 4.
- Malhotra & Haidar (n.d). *CS:Theory and Practice*(5th ed).
- Mushtaq, I., & Khan, S. N. (2012). Factors Affecting Students Academic performance. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research*, 2-3.
- Mutairi, A. A. (2011). Factors Affecting Business Students' Performance in Arab Open University: The case of Kuwait International Journal of Business and Management.
- Russell, C. D. (2012). Gender, AA, and Meanings of Schooling in Ras al Khaimah, United Arab Emirates.
- Tabish, M., & Iqbal, T. (2015). English Language Learning Proficiency of Rural Learner Compared to Urban: a Case Study of Management Students. *Journal of Science & Management*, 2-3.